

SHORT NOTES

Piperidine Complexes of Thiocyanates of Zinc, Cadmium, Cobalt and Nickel

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Freshly prepared thiocyanates of zinc, cadmium, cobalt and nickel were refluxed with pure and dry piperidine and the solution obtained was filtered hot. In case of cadmium and nickel the hot filtrate on cooling yielded beautiful crystals of complexes. But in case of zinc and cobalt complexes, the hot filtrate on concentration gave a pasty mass which did not crystallise even when left in vacuum desiccator for several days. An alternative procedure was, therefore, adopted. The hot filtrate was cooled in a stoppered flask for a day. An equal volume of pure and dry ether was then added to the clear solution. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and kept in a cooled place. The complex separated slowly in crystalline form after a few hours.

The complexes on chemical analysis were found to correspond to the following formulae: $Zn(CNS)_2 \cdot 2Pip$, $Cd(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$, $Co(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$ and $Ni(CNS)_2 \cdot 4Pip$.

While zinc and cadmium complexes are colourless those of cobalt and nickel possess bright pink and green colour respectively. All of them are almost insoluble in water, acetone, benzene, carbon tetrachloride but are sparingly soluble in chloroform.

Thermogravimetric studies indicate that these complexes are stable at room temperature but start losing piperidine at about 50°C. and at about 300°C. all the piperidine is lost above which metallic thiocyanates themselves begin to decompose.

